

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ORGANIZING THE DISTANCE EDUCATION PROCESS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotation

The article describes the possibilities of using distance education in the educational process of preschool educational organizations, which provides an opportunity to use information and communication technologies during training and increase the effectiveness of education on this basis.

Keywords: computer, distance education, presentation, innovation, education, multimedia.

I. INTRODUCTION

Pre-school education is not only the first type of continuous education, but also the first step in forming a creative, socially active, spiritually rich person. In the current period of globalization and development of computer technologies, various technologies provide an opportunity to be successfully used in virtual space. Distance education is an excellent form of education based on new information technologies and multimedia systems. Modern telecommunication and electronic publishing overcomes the disadvantages of traditional teaching systems while incorporating their advantages.

Article 5 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" states "Supporting innovative activities in educational organizations and implementation of educational programs using innovative technologies", and Article 46 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" states that "use of information and communication technologies, advanced and innovative methods of education and training" the use of forms and methods"¹ - it was emphasized.

Action strategy for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Development of education and science" section of the direction of social sphere development states "Further improvement of the continuing education system, increasing the opportunities for quality education services, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in line with the modern needs of the labor market, general The

tasks of "fundamental improvement of the quality of secondary education, in-depth study of foreign languages, computer science and other important and high-demand subjects such as mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology" are defined.²

On the urgency of using multimedia technology in the field of education, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020 on the approval of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy and measures for its effective implementation No. "establishing special media centers producing educational content and multimedia educational products (audiobooks, 3D, VR, etc.)"³

In the decision PQ-4851 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of October 6, 2020 "On measures to further improve the education system in the field of information technologies, develop scientific research and integrate them with the IT industry", "Improving the system of training personnel in the field of information technologies" Digital Uzbekistan — is one of the important conditions for the successful implementation of the "2030" strategy, the development of digital technologies and ensuring their widespread introduction into the daily life of the population.⁴

Article 53 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Preschool Education and Training" defines the tasks of providing the system of preschool education and training from a scientific and methodological point of view, including the introduction of advanced pedagogical and information technologies into the

¹ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" September 23, 2020, ORQ-637 <https://lex.uz/docs/5013007>

² On the strategy of actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – T.: Justice, 2017. -111 b.

³ Decree No. PF-6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020 "On approval of the

Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy and measures for its effective implementation. <https://lex.uz/docs/5030957>

⁴ Decision No. PQ-4851 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 6, 2020 "On measures to further improve the educational system in the field of information technology, develop scientific research and integrate it with the IT industry".. <https://lex.uz/docs/5032128>

educational process, educational and methodological and development and production of didactic materials, conducting scientific research in the field of preschool education and upbringing, development and introduction of modern methods of preschool education and upbringing management.⁵

Today, the use of computers and modern information technologies, telecommunication networks, data transfer, reception and Internet services is considered as a requirement of the time.

Distance education is applied to general secondary education, secondary special vocational and higher education types of continuous education, however, the possibilities of using distance education in preschool education, the first type of continuous education, are not sufficiently illuminated. Due to the fact that the possibilities of using distance education in pre-school education organizations are not sufficiently studied, the study and research of this topic is an urgent issue.

Innovative methods, tools and teaching forms based on computer and telecommunication technologies are used in the process of distance education.

Distance education was first implemented by our great ancestors Ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Al Khorazmi and others. They were giving knowledge and assignments to their students in other cities through letters (with the help of pigeons). But it took weeks and months to exchange information by letter.

This tradition among scientists continued until the invention of the telegraph, radio and television. In the present period, distance education based on computer technology, information telecommunication and Internet system is being implemented, just like the level of full-time education.

Distance education is based on distance learning.

Distance education is a type of goal-oriented learning that requires the use of special teaching tools, communication with the teacher by phone, email or simple chat, studying at the place of your choice with a personal schedule, intensive, independent work on yourself.

Distance education based on information and telecommunication tools has the following advantages:

- There is a possibility of deeper and more perfect mastering of the given materials;
- Passion for close contact with new areas of learning will increase;
- As a result of reducing the time of education, the opportunity to save time is achieved;
- Individual activities of students were observed during the educational process;
- Allows the user to receive training at any time (for example, in his free time);
- Allows the use of electronic educational resources;
- In the process of education, the user's ability to work independently develops;
- Allows full use of computer technologies;
- Ensures achieving economic savings;

Distance education is open education. Open education or open learning environment is an educational system in which the educational process is goal-oriented, controlled and characterized by strong (intensive) independent work of the learner. In open education, the learner has the opportunity to choose the program, teacher's training schedule and form.

II. STUDY OF THE SUBJECT

Distance education has been reflected in many literatures. In particular, well-known scientists in this field in our Republic: A.A. Abdugadirov, A.Kh. Pardaev, as well as L.P. Korenev, E.V. Semina, E.V. Eldasheva, H. Rashidov, U.Sh. Begimkulov, N.I.Taylakov, J.Sayfiev, O.N.Rozimorodov, T.Haidarov and others' works have a special place. Just as the invention of pen and paper once brought education to a new level, information technology has brought about a new revolution in today's society. In education, telecommunication and computer technologies have opened the way to new forms of information representation and transmission. One of the main forms is online education called "distance learning".

Distance education is the provision of a set of educational services to a wide range of people in the country and abroad with the help of a special information-educational environment based on means of exchange of educational information (computer communication, satellite television, etc.) between the student and the teacher. Features of distance education include, firstly, the distance

⁵ Ordinance of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 16, 2019 "On preschool education and

training" No. RQ-595.(National database of legal documents, 17.12.2019, No. 03/19/595/4160)

between the student and the teacher; secondly, independence - some variant of the form of part-time education; thirdly, it is the active integration of media and materials into the educational process.

How important can psychological-pedagogical technologies be in distance education? In the virtual space, they can also perform a task that activates the learning process, but at a new level, that is, it must meet the requirements of the virtual environment and integrate with information technology. The latest technologies can cause a sharp uproar among experts in countries where they have been integrated into the educational process for a long time. It is important for them how modern technical and information media affect students. According to French experts, they have the following advantages when using the latest technologies in education:

- increases the motivation of teaching;
- is a source of information, encourages independent learning, forms independent and focused skills;
- increases the informativeness, intensity, and effectiveness of education.

At the same time, many experts are far from idealizing the importance of modern technologies and even question their use. For example, the Japanese pedagogue S. Suzuki believes that, on the one hand, the computer develops students' thinking, and on the other hand, it provides knowledge consolidation. The French pedagogue L. Legrand studied the phenomenon of students' motivation in working on the computer and offers to analyze the issue of whether the game that appears in it is learning or not. In addition, excessive computer training irritates the user and affects eye function. It is important not to forget that it causes such negative consequences. In general, foreign experts are of the same opinion on the need for a comprehensive approach to the analysis of modern teaching tools, which implies the high-quality training and retraining of teachers, as well as the cooperation of scientists, pedagogues and specialists in the field of new technologies.

III. METHODS

Therefore, the possibilities of distance education are many, for example, the time it takes for educators to develop certain skills is reduced, the number of tasks to be performed from a

practical point of view increases somewhat, as a result of requiring active control by the computer, the student becomes a subject of education, the possibility of providing the lesson with remote resources using communication tools is created. at the same time, the most important thing is that the pace of independent work of educators will accelerate.

Below we will look at some examples and some problems of distance education and the use of the Internet in preschool educational institutions.

1) Use of computer games: For example, the presentation "Whose house is where" taken from the Internet is dedicated to the comparison of numbers within 10 numbers for 6-7-year-old children in the field of mathematics. Вазифа: белги-кўрсаткичлар < ёки > ларга биноан рақамлар уйларга жойлаштирилишлари керак.

In the course of the game, part of the animated numbers move and one by one gather in front of the first house, and the other parts gather in front of the second house. This last case is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Presentation of whose house is where

Students will learn the concept that numbers are signs of number from the plot of this presentation game.

The second game: consists of making geometric figures from triangle, rectangle, square, circle, ellipse (compressed circle) shapes.

Task: Make a house, a flower, a rabbit, a mouse, a tree, a cat, a phone, a fish, a mushroom, a truck.

Execution: By opening the above frames taken from the Internet and stored in the computer memory, the 10 figures highlighted above are created one after another from the geometric

shapes of different colors, which are animated on the screen and are explained (questions and answers) by the pleasant voice of the singer.

Picture 2 shows a picture of one of these "built houses". The "constructed house" in Figure 2 is composed of two rectangles, one square, one triangle and one circle. From this game, preschoolers will get elementary understanding of geometric shapes and figures.

Figure 2. Making geometric figures from triangle, rectangle, square, circle, ellipse (compressed circle) shapes

In addition to the above games, there are several issues related to distance learning and Internet use in preschools.

1. Since multimedia pedagogical technology is based on computer education, it is necessary to ensure that children have the minimum knowledge and skills in using it. For this, the teacher himself must have sufficient computer literacy. Educators can implement computer literacy using "computer lessons" in distance learning materials.

2. Using the distance education system, educators of preschool education organizations in remote areas can communicate with educators of preschool education organizations in central cities and exchange experience.

3. Educators and pedagogues of the distance education system of pre-school education organization can actively participate in the video conferences held in this field to improve the educational process and share experience. For this, one of the leading preschool education organizations in the republic should organize this video conference.

IV. CONCLUSION

Thus, there are opportunities to apply distance education system and Internet resources to the educational processes of preschool educational organizations. If this problem is fully resolved, the effectiveness of educational activities conducted in preschool educational organizations will increase.

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